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STARCH/GRAPHENE HYDROGELS VIA CLICK CHEMISTRY WITH RELEVANT ELECTRICAL AND ANTIBACTERIAL PROPERTIES

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Abstract

Starch-based hydrogels were performed by Diels-Alder cross-linking reactions between furan-modified starch and a water soluble bismaleimide, with improving conducting properties by using graphene layers as active nanofillers. The characterization results demonstrated that the Diels-Alder reaction and the corresponding conditions for the hydrogel formation were appropriate. The effect of increasing the furan/maleimide ratio on the architecture of the hydrogels and on the morphological, rheological and swelling properties was thoroughly evaluated. Effective network structure was obtained by increasing the cross-linker content leading

to decreasing pore size and increasing storage modulus value of the final material. It was shown that the swelling behavior of hydrogels was mainly governed by the hydrophilic character of bismaleimide. Graphene nanosheets were added for the synthesis of nanocomposite hydrogel and it was characterized in terms of rheological properties, electrical conductivity and antimicrobial activity. The nanocomposite hydrogel presented enhanced mechanical performance, antimicrobial activity and increased conductivity values, up to a decade, indicating that conductive and active hydrogels could be satisfactorily obtained, for a large range of potential applications such as biomed.

Keywords

Furan-modified starch, Diels-Alder, cross-linking, graphene, electrical response.

1. Introduction

Historically, platinum, gold and platinum/iridium electrodes have been used e.g., in neuronal interfaces (Aregueta-Robles, Woolley, Poole-Warren, Lovell, & Green, 2014). However, and nowadays, new smaller devices with improved mechanical, electrical and biological properties are required. Due to the necessity to overcome some limitations of traditional metallic electrodes (low charge injection, mechanical mismatch or foreign body response) employed for neuronal interfaces (Aregueta-Robles et al., 2014), several coating materials are being investigated such as conductive polymers or hydrogels, bioactive coatings and tissue engineered neural interfaces. As reported in literature (Ganguly et al., 2018), electrical conductive hydrogels could be developed by the incorporation of conductive carbonaceous particles such as carbon nanotubes or graphene (G). G is a single layer of sp^2 bonded carbon atoms packed in a two dimensional honeycomb lattice (Grande et al., 2017; Ji, Sun, & Qu, 2016; Zheng, Ma, & Ma, 2013), which presents unique mechanical and electrical properties (Ganguly et al., 2018).

As it is well known, hydrogels are three-dimensional (3D) hydrophilic polymeric networks which are able to swell and retain large amount of water or biological fluids, maintaining their specific 3D structure in water-based medium (Dragan, 2014; Li, Tan, Xu, Lu, & Wang, 2017; Ullah, Othman, Javed, Zulkifli, & Akil, 2015). The

so-called “smart hydrogels” display an extra benefit to the material showing e.g., stimuli response to external factors such as temperature, pH, and/or electric field (Liang et al., 2015). Specifically conductive hydrogels, present the ability to conduct electricity under certain conditions while maintaining their dimensional stability, and find applicability in relevant research fields such as biomedicine, biomaterials, bioengineering and controlled drug delivery (Liang et al., 2015).

Hydrogels could be classified as physical and chemical hydrogels, depending on the nature of the crosslinking. Physical hydrogels form the 3D network through non-covalent interactions between chains (Xiao, 2013), i.e. hydrogen bonding or hydrophobic interactions (Ahmed, 2015). On the contrary, chemical hydrogels are obtained by either ionic cross-linking or covalent bonding, normally through the reaction of the polymer with a low molar mass cross-linker (Ullah et al., 2015; Xiao, 2013).

Covalent bonding in chemical hydrogels is usually performed using strong reaction conditions, with required cross-linker agents, which often could be considered as toxic (Ullah et al., 2015; Xiao, 2013). These inconveniences restricts the application areas of the developed materials (Xiao, 2013). However, several strategies are proposed for the formation of hydrogels based on environmentally friendly, non-toxic and biodegradable polymers. Among them, the use of ‘click’ chemistry, in particular the Diels-Alder (DA) reaction is receiving increased attention due to the high selectivity, versatility and yielding reaction (Anseth & Klok, 2016). DA reactions is defined as the thermoreversible cycloaddition between a diene and a dienophile (García-Astrain & Avérous, 2018), which proceed in mild temperatures, aqueous environment, free of catalysts or initiators and without undesirable side reactions (García-Astrain et al., 2016a). The DA ‘click’ coupling reaction is often carried out using furans as dienes and maleimides as dienophiles. Therefore, ‘click’ hydrogels require the polymer to be properly functionalized with specific chemical groups (Xiao, 2013).

In this sense, the use of biopolymers (IUPAC definition: polymers formed by living organisms, from biomass) is gaining attention due to their biodegradability, biocompatibility, accessibility, low-cost and because they show interesting functional groups ready for functionalization and/or cross-linking (Ahmed, 2015; Xiao, 2013).

In addition, hydrogels synthesized with biopolymers from renewable resources show mechanical and rheological properties similar of those of human tissues (García-Astrain et al., 2015a).

In the last years, several biopolymers have been investigated for the formation of hydrogels, such as proteins (collagen, gelatin) or polysaccharides (alginate, agarose, chitosan) (Ahmed, 2015) also using 'click' chemistry reactions. Yu et al. (2013), reported the preparation of hydrogels based on gelatin suitable for cartilage tissue engineering by DA reaction. Guaresti et al. (2017 & 2018) proposed different strategies to obtain hydrogels from chitosan by using the DA reaction with promising results for applications on drug delivery systems.

Starch is one of the most abundant biopolymer, it is biodegradable and inexpensive and possesses both primary and secondary hydroxyl groups suitable for being reacted in order to add specific functionality (Xiao, 2013). Liebert et al., (2005) and Hesse et al., (2006) reported the modification of different polysaccharides based on furan-2-carboxylic acid esters, among which stands out the reaction with starch. However, although furan modification of starch was performed, few works have been reported focusing on the DA reaction from the furan-functionalized starch (Nossa et al, 2015) and, far as we know, none referring to hydrogels. Native starch shows poor water solubility due to a specific 3D crystalline organization. Its hydrophilic character results in the ability to retain large amount of water upon heating (Abhari, Madadlou, Dini, & Hosseini naveh, 2017). With specific physicochemical and biological behaviors, starch seem to be an excellent candidate for the formation of hydrogels with applications in different areas such as biomedicine (Li et al., 2017).

G or graphene oxide has been used in combination with biopolymers to develop films, foams or hydrogels obtaining conductive materials (Gao, Mei, Ma, Yuan, & Ren, 2017; Lim, Huang, & Loo, 2012; Riaz, Usman, & Hussain, 2016; Ugarte et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2014b). In addition to its unique electronic transport properties, G and its derivatives are promising materials to be use in biomedical applications due to their antimicrobial behavior (Pang, Dai, Bi, Guo, & Fan, 2017). Hegab et al. (2016) defined that the antimicrobial capacity of G containing materials is caused by the chemical and physical interactions between G nanosheets and the bacteria cell membranes. The antimicrobial mechanism seem to be caused by the charge transfer and bacterial migration, as well as by the extraction of phospholipids from the cell membranes due to the insertion

of G into the cells (Pang et al., 2017). However, G presents poor dispersability in polar solvents and water (Ganguly et al., 2018; Grande et al., 2017). Several approaches had been reported focusing on the dispersion of graphene in aqueous solutions as alternative to the oxidation of G sheets, by using different types of surfactants. Among them, those containing phenolic moieties had been reported to be highly “graphene-philic” due to π - π interactions, leading to higher dispersion stabilities (Mohamed et al., 2018). In this context, natural plant extracts could be used as dispersion stabilizers looking for the required water dispersability as they content high concentration of polyphenolic compounds. Indeed, it was demonstrated that *Salvia officinalis* L. can act as surfactant due to the presence of specific groups on its chemical structure (Santamaria-Echart et al., 2018). In addition, *Salvia*, as well as other medicinal plants, show antimicrobial or anti-inflammatory activity (Martins et al., 2014), relevant properties in biomedical applications.

Thereby, we hypothesize that ‘click’ chemistry could be an interesting strategy for obtaining starch-based chemically cross-linked hydrogels between furan-modified starch and a bismaleimide (BMI) compound. Thus, the first aim of this work was the furan-functionalization of starch by reaction of gelatinized starch (S) with furfuryl isocyanate (FI). Then, cross-linked hydrogels were obtained by aqueous DA reaction using a water soluble BMI. Considering that the effectiveness of the cross-linked network could be affected by the furan/maleimide (Fu:Mal) weight ratio, different cross-linker amounts were used in order to analyze its influence in the rheological behavior, morphology and swelling capacity of the hydrogels. We further hypothesize that the addition of G sheets into the matrix could result in improved antimicrobial and electrical properties. Thus, nanocomposite hydrogels were prepared with G as nanofiller by using *Salvia* extracts as stabilizer.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

GMO-free native maize starch containing 73% amylopectin and 27% amylose, furfuryl isocyanate (97%), Jeffamine[®] ED 900 (O,O'-bis (2-aminopropyl) polypropylene glycol-b-polyethylene glycol-b-polypropylene glycol, number-average molar mass = 900 g/mol), sodium acetate trihydrate ($\geq 99.0\%$), graphite flakes, N-

methyl pyrrolidone (NMP, 97%) and deuterium oxide (D₂O) (deuteration degree min. 99.96%) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (USA). Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, for analysis), maleic anhydride, trimethylamine (99.5%), acetic anhydride (98 %), acetone (for analysis) and the phosphate buffered saline (PBS) tablets were provided by Panreac (Spain). Chloroform (99.8%) was purchased from Lab Scan Analytical Sciences (Poland). Distilled water was used as solvent. All reagents and solvents were employed as received.

2.2. Furan-functionalization of starch

Furan-modified starch was synthesized by the reaction of S with FI with the method described by Nossa et al. (2015). Firstly, S was obtained by gelatinization-casting methodology described previously (González et al., 2017; González, Retegi, González, Eceiza, & Gabilondo, 2015) with slight modifications. 2 g of native maize starch were dispersed in 30 ml of distilled water. The mixture was gelatinized under continuous magnetic stirring at 90 °C during 40 min. After that, the viscous gel was homogenized in a dispersing system for 3 min at 15000 rpm (POLYTRON[®] PT 2500 E). The gel was spread into petri dishes and dried in an oven at 70 °C for 5 h.

After that, 0.45 g of S were dissolved in 6.4 ml of DMSO and the corresponding amount of FI in a 1:0.1 starch to furfuryl isocyanate molar ratio (S:FI) (based on the molar mass of anhydrous glucose i.e., 162 g/mol) (Nossa et al., 2015). The reaction was allowed to proceed at 60 °C for 2 h with continuous stirring (Scheme 1a). After that, the product was precipitated and washed with ethanol, and then, it was dissolved in distilled water and purified by dialysis (Spectra Por 12000–14000 MWCO regenerated cellulose dialysis membranes from Spectrum Laboratories, USA) against distilled water for 24 h. The resulting product was dried at 30 °C for 24 h.

Scheme 1. a) Synthesis of furan-modified starch and b) DA cross-linking reaction of S-FI and BMI.

2.3. Synthesis of water soluble BMI

The synthesis of the water soluble BMI cross-linker was performed following the method developed by García-Astrain et al. (2014). Briefly, 25.87 mmol of Jeffamine® ED 900 were added dropwise over 50 ml of maleic anhydride solution (50.97 mmol) in chloroform. The reaction was maintained at 10 °C for 3 h under nitrogen. Then, the product was kept under magnetic stirring at room temperature for 2 h and dried under vacuum. 4.56 mmol of the dried product, bismaleamic acid, were mixed with trimethylamine (2.96 mmol) and sodium acetate trihydrate (3.47 mmol) in 10 ml of acetone under nitrogen. Acetic anhydride (28.96 mmol) was then added and the reaction was maintained at 70 °C for 2.5 h. The BMI was obtained by solvent evaporation under vacuum.

2.4. Hydrogel formation by DA reaction between S-FI and BMI

Starch-based hydrogels were obtained by the DA reaction of S-FI and the BMI cross-linker (Scheme 1b). 0.128 g of S-FI were dissolved in 2 ml of distilled water (6 wt. %) overnight. Then, the hydrogel was obtained by mixing the S-FI aqueous solution and the desired amount of BMI and allowed to react at 65 °C for 24 h in a closed vial.

Three different hydrogels were prepared with different S-FI:BMI weight ratios (Fu:Mal), 1:0.5; 1:1.0 and 1:1.5. The S-FI/Jeffamine® ED 900 weight ratio of 1:0.5 was also prepared at the same temperature and time cycle as the reference (control). The corresponding hydrogels were named as HSFI-1:0.5, HSFI-1:1.0, HSFI-1:1.5 and HSFI-Control, respectively. In order to evaluate the influence of the bismaleimide content, the hydrogels were characterized as-prepared.

2.5. Preparation of nanocomposites based on DA hydrogel

Conductive nanocomposite hydrogels were prepared by adding G into the reactive mixture. The preparation of Salvia extracts was carried out by infusion method according to the protocol described by Santamaria-Echart et al. (2018). 20 g of *Salvia Officinalis L.* were boiled with distilled water for 5 minutes. After that, the obtained suspension was filtered and freeze-dried. The exfoliation of G was performed as described by Ugarte et al.

(2017). Briefly, 20 g of G were sonicated in NMP. The obtained dispersion was centrifuged at 4000 rpm and the supernatant was filtered, washed with acetone and dried at room temperature for 48 h.

G and Salvia extracts aqueous dispersion was prepared by ultrasonication for 6 h. 0.128 g of S-FI was then dissolved in the aqueous dispersion and 0.192 g of BMI was added in a 1:1.5 weight ratio. The reaction was performed at 65 °C for 24 h in a closed vial. G and extracts contents were 0.2 wt.% relative to the (S-FI + BMI) total weight. The nanocomposite hydrogel will be referred as HSFI-1:1.5GE.

2.6. Characterization

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) was performed in a Nicolet Nexus 380 FT-IR. Measurements were recorded in the range from 4000 to 650 cm^{-1} in attenuated reflection mode, with a 4 cm^{-1} resolution and 32 scans.

Proton Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (^1H NMR) was used to analyze the chemical structure of the samples. The measurements were performed with an Avance Bruker equipped with BBO z-gradient probe. Experimental conditions were a frequency of 500 MHz, a number of scans of 64, a spectral window of 5000 Hz, and a recovery delay of 1 s. D_2O was used as solvent in all cases. ^1H NMR results were also employed to calculate the degree of substitution (DS) of the functionalized starch. DS could be defined as the average number of substituted units per glucose monomer (Tizzotti, Sweedman, Tang, Schaefer, & Gilbert, 2011). The DS was determined by the integration of the α -anomeric hydrogen signal of the glucose unit.

UV-VIS spectrophotometry was mainly used to follow the DA reaction between the furan-modified starch and the BMI, using a Shimadzu UV-3600/3100 instrument equipped with a thermoelectric cell holder, operating at 65 °C in a range of 200 to 400 nm and recording spectra every 30 minutes during 24 h.

The rheological properties of the hydrogels were studied ($n = 3$) using a Scientific Advanced Rheometric Expansion System (ARES), using a plate-plate geometry (25 mm diameter). Frequency sweep measurements were performed at 37 °C from 0.1 to 500 rad s^{-1} at a fixed strain, in the linear viscoelastic region, previously assessed by stress sweep experiments.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) images were obtained in a VEGA3 LM, TESCAN equipment with an operation voltage of 5 kV. Samples were previously gold coated.

The swelling capacity of the hydrogels ($n = 3$) was determined by gravimetric method. Freeze-dried hydrogels were incubated at 37 °C until equilibrium using simulated intestinal fluid, PBS at pH = 7.4. At selected time intervals, the swollen hydrogels were removed, the excess of water absorbed with a filter paper, and then weighed. The swelling ratio (SR) was determined by Equation 1:

$$SR (\%) = \frac{W_s - W_t}{W_t} \times 100 \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

where W_s is the weight of the swollen sample and W_t is the weight of the dried sample. The equilibrium swelling was considered to be achieved when the weight of the hydrogels no longer increased.

The hydrolytic degradation of hydrogels was also studied gravimetrically incubating the samples in PBS for one week and calculated from Equation 2:

$$\text{Degradation} (\%) = \frac{W_t}{W_d} \times 100 \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

where W_d is the initial weight of the freeze-dried sample.

Antimicrobial activity of the samples against both *Escherichia coli* CECT 405 (*E. coli*, gram positive bacteria) and *Staphylococcus aureus* CECT 239 (*S. aureus*, gram negative bacteria) was analyzed following the disc-plate antibiogram test. The hydrogel was placed in the inoculated agar of a petri dish containing the microorganism to be tested. The samples were then incubated at 37 °C for 24 and 48 h.

The electrical conductivity of the hydrogels was analyzed by a Keithley 4200-SCS equipment (USA) for semiconductor analysis using a two points measurements technique. The measurements of wet hydrogels were performed working at 0-5 V linear scans, with 0.01 V step and a compliance of 0.1 A.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Analysis of the functionalized starch

Furanic starch derivative was obtained from reaction of S with FI in DMSO using a molar ratio of 1:0.1. (Nossa et al., 2015). The obtained functionalized starch was analyzed by ^1H NMR.

^1H NMR analysis was performed to corroborate the chemical structure of the modified sample and to determine the DS. ^1H NMR spectra of gelatinized starch and the furanic derivative are presented in Figures 1a and 1b, respectively. Starch is characterized by the presence of a peak at 5.34 ppm corresponding to the α -anomeric hydrogen (peak A in the Figure 1a) and a multiple peak at 3.3 - 4.0 ppm region, associated to the six other hydrogens of the anhydroglucose unit (Jordan, Schmidt, Liebert, & Heinze, 2014). New peaks related to the furan ring were observed at 7.46, 6.40 and 6.28 ppm for the modified starch (Figure 1b) (García-Astrain et al., 2014; García-Astrain et al., 2016c; Nossa et al., 2015). According to the literature, the primary hydroxyl (OH) group at C6 is more reactive than the secondary OH at C2 and C3 (Jordan et al., 2014). Hence, the insertion of the furanic molecule is likely to occur at that position varying the intensity of the signal located at 4.0 ppm. The integration value of the furanic protons relative to that of the α -anomeric hydrogen signal, the DS value, was found to be 0.04. Several attempts were performed in order to optimize the final DS value by increasing the furfuryl isocyanate content. However, as the DS value did not further increase from 0.04, the 1:0.1 ratio was finally used. Thus, according to ^1H NMR results, it was concluded that the furan-modification of starch was successfully performed.

Fig. 1. ^1H RMN spectra of a) gelatinized starch and b) whole scan range (left) and magnification from 8 to 6 ppm (right) of the furanic starch derivative (Temperature = room temperature, solvent = D_2O).

3.2. Analysis of the synthesized hydrogels

Several hydrogels were prepared with different Fu:Mal weight ratios similarly to the previous work based on furan modified gelatin, with some modifications (C. García-Astrain et al., 2014). Besides, a reference sample (control) was prepared by mixing the Jeffamine[®] ED 900 with S-FI using a weight ratio of 1:0.5 in order to control the success of the DA cross-linking reaction.

All the targeted hydrogels were successfully synthesized by DA reaction after the reaction time, whereas the control sample remained in a liquid state.

The corresponding hydrogels were analyzed by FTIR. The resulting spectra are shown in Figure 2. Due to the number of the signals in the same region the new peaks were hardly distinguishable and, hence, the magnification in the range of $2000\text{-}600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is then presented.

For all cross-linked hydrogels new peaks of carbonyl maleimide group ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) could be observed at 1745 and 1706 cm^{-1} (García-Astrain et al., 2015b). In addition, new peaks related to the stretching vibration of the double bond ($\text{C}=\text{C}$) in the DA adduct appeared at 1455 cm^{-1} (Fan et al., 2015; Guaresti et al., 2017; Guaresti et al., 2018; Nimmo, Owen, & Shoichet, 2011), as well as a new peak associated with ether group (C-O-C) stretching vibration of the DA adduct at 1100 cm^{-1} (García-Astrain et al., 2015b).

Fig. 2. Magnification of the FTIR spectra of BMI, S-FI and the three final cross-linked starch hydrogels at room temperature.

The DA reaction was followed by UV-VIS spectroscopy. The reaction between the furan-modified starch and the BMI was monitored using a temperature-controlled device. A spectrum was recovered each 30 minutes, during 24 h. The measurements were carried out at 65 °C using the Fu:Mal weight ratio of 1:1.5 as the reference. Figure 3 shows the obtained UV-VIS spectra for each probe time.

As reported in literature, the maleimide ring shows an absorbance maximum close to $\lambda = 300$ nm (Engel & Kickelbick, 2013; García-Astrain et al., 2014) associated to the conjugated effect of the double bond $\pi\pi^*$ (C=C) and the two carbonyl groups $\pi\pi^*$ (C=O) chromophore excitations (Gandini, Silvestre, & Coelho, 2008; García-Astrain et al., 2015a). As the reaction proceeds, the mentioned conjugation between the double bonds would disappear due to the formation of the DA adduct, with the subsequent decrease of the signal intensity (Engel & Kickelbick, 2013; Gandini, Coelho, Gomes, Reis, & Silvestre, 2009; Vilela, Cruciani, Silvestre, & Gandini, 2012). Thus, the evolution of the DA reaction could be analyzed, monitoring the variation of the intensity of the maleimide absorbance band in time.

As illustrated in Figure 3, the absorbance band related to the maleimide groups decreased progressively as the cross-linking reaction proceeded to form the DA adduct. The intensity of the absorbance band decreased

until disappearing at the end of the reaction. The results proved that the DA reaction occurred completely and the success of the proposed strategy was then assessed.

Fig. 3. UV-VIS spectra of the evolution of the DA reaction at 65 °C.

3.3. Analysis of the effect of Fu:Mal ratio on hydrogel properties

The viscoelastic behavior of the hydrogels ($n = 3$) was analyzed in connection with the Fu:Mal weight ratio. The influence of the amount of cross-linker in the stiffness of the hydrogels was evaluated. Firstly, preliminary strain sweep tests were carried out in order to determine the linear viscoelastic region of each sample, i.e. the region in which both the storage (G') and loss modulus (G'') were independent of the applied strain. Thus, a constant strain of 1% was selected to perform the frequency sweep tests. Results are shown in Figure 4. As observed, after a small period of stabilization the samples showed a solid-like gel behavior (Mandal et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2014b) which is characteristic of an elastic pattern. The G' was maintained almost constant and always higher than G'' in the whole studied frequency range (0.1 – 500 rad/s) (García-Astrain et al., 2016c). Some noticeable differences were observed between the different hydrogels. When comparing HSFI-1:0.5 and HSFI-1:1.0 hydrogels, it was found that G' values were 1720 ± 243 Pa and 1600 ± 173 Pa, respectively. However, increasing the BMI amount up to the 1:1.5 weight ratio resulted in higher G' values (3750 ± 353 Pa). The value of the G' is generally assumed to be closely related to the cross-linking density of the hydrogel network (García-

Astrain et al., 2016a). Hence, the remarkable increase in the G' value for the 1:1.5 sample could be ascribed to a larger amount of cross-linking points.

The field of application of hydrogels synthesized from biodegradable polymers is mainly related to biomedical applications as scaffolds or implants. It is therefore of great relevance the rigidity of the final material as it could be directly affecting its final performance. G' , as indicator of this rigidity, was found to be in the range between 1600 to 3750 Pa, which are comparable with those values of liver, fat, relaxed muscle and breast gland tissue (10^3 - 10^4 Pa) (García-Astrain et al., 2015a).

Fig. 4. Frequency sweep measurements of ■ HSFI-1:0.5, ● HSFI-1:1.0 and ▲ HSFI-1:1.5 results of G' (filled symbols) and G'' (empty symbols). Tests conditions: 37 °C and 10 Hz.

As previously pointed out in the literature (García-Astrain et al., 2014), an interconnected porous structure is desirable for hydrogels to be applied as drug carriers or scaffolds, as the porous network would facilitate the transport and delivery of required molecules (Bai et al., 2017). Therefore, the microstructure of hydrogels was studied by SEM. Samples were freeze-dried after swollen in distilled water. It is generally accepted that, the interconnected domains occupied by water in the swollen samples, changed after the freeze-drying process to a porous structure due to the ice crystals formation (Fan et al., 2015). Figure 5 shows the microstructure of each sample analyzed by SEM.

As noticed, the morphology of hydrogels was strongly influenced by the amount of the cross-linker. A porous structure was obtained in all cases, which is expected to retain a great amount of water (Bai et al., 2017). However, as it could be observed, increasing the Fu:Mal weight ratio led to a more porous structure. HSFI-1:0.5 sample showed a quite compact morphology with both smooth areas and pits, whereas for HSFI-1:1.0 and HSFI-1:1.5 hydrogels a homogeneous porous microstructure was observed. Moreover, the pore size was found to be much smaller for the latter (around 10 μm for HSFI-1:1.0 and around 25 μm for HSFI-1:1.5) being them regularly distributed along the sample. It is normally accepted that the use of higher amounts of cross-linker in the formulations led to smaller pore sizes since higher cross-linking densities are obtained (Bai et al., 2017). Hence, these results would be in concordance with those previously presented from the rheological data, and therefore, could indicate that the 1:1.5 Fu:Mal weight ratio achieved the highest degree of cross-linking, showing the highest elastic modulus value and the smaller pore size.

Fig. 5. SEM images of the porous microstructure of starch based hydrogels HSFI-1:0.5, HSFI-1:1.0 and HSFI-1:1.5 samples (White bars = 50 microns).

The swelling behavior is one of the most important property to be evaluated in hydrogels (G.-F. Wang et al., 2014; Wei et al., 2010), in particular when they are used for biomedical applications (Yu et al., 2014). The swelling capacity of the hydrogels was gravimetrically measured by swelling freeze-dried samples ($n = 3$) in simulated intestinal fluid (phosphate buffer (PBS), $\text{pH} = 7.4$ at 37°C). The SR was determined by the Equation 1. The obtained swelling curves are shown in Figure 6.

The swelling patterns of all samples involved two steps of different swelling rates. During the first step, the SR increased fast up to a value of 400 % for the 1:0.5 hydrogel and 800 % for the other two, whereas in the second

step the swelling degree grew slowly until the equilibrium was achieved. The equilibrium value was reached after similar time interval in all cases.

As reported elsewhere (García-Astrain et al., 2016a; Yu et al., 2013; García-Astrain et al., 2014; García-Astrain et al., 2015b), the SR depends on both the employed external stimuli (ionic strength, pH, temperature) and the nature of the polymer, i.e. the hydrophilic character of the polymer, the concentration, the cross-linking density of the network and the porosity of the hydrogel. In our case, the cross-linking density and the hydrophilic nature of the BMI would be decisive variables. Commonly the SR decreases when a highly cross-linked network is obtained, since the 3D network hinders the permeation of the solution inside the hydrogel (García-Astrain et al., 2016a; Yu et al., 2013). At the same time, the hydrogen bonds that easily formed between the hydrophilic polymeric chains and water molecules brought the solution inside the network leading to higher SR (Yu et al., 2013).

According to the rheological results and the microstructure analysis, higher cross-linker densities were attributed to the hydrogel with the largest amount of BMI. Thus, it could be expected that lower SR values would be obtained for higher Fu:Mal weight ratios. However, in our case the opposite effect was observed (Figure 1), i.e. the SR increased when using higher BMI amounts. Consequently, the HSFI-1:1.5 sample is the one with higher swelling degree. The strong hydrophilic character of the used cross-linker is likely to be the main reason for these swelling behavior, in agreement with previously reported literature (García-Astrain et al., 2016b; Guaresti et al., 2018).

In order to evaluate the long-term stability of the hydrogels, they were maintained immersed in PBS ($n = 3$) for one week and the hydrolytic degradation was assessed by determining the final weight loss. Similar degradation values (in %) were obtained for HSFI-1:1.0 ($53 \pm 2\%$) and HSFI-1:1.5 ($52 \pm 5\%$) hydrogels, whereas remarkable values were achieved for HSFI-1:0.5 sample ($79 \pm 1\%$). These results are in concordance with the literature (Fan et al., 2015; Nimmo et al., 2011), which stated that the degradation is influenced by the cross-linker network, thus higher cross-linked network result in lower degradation values.

Fig. 6. SR (%) versus time curves of obtained starch hydrogels in PBS at 37 °C.

3.4. Analysis of the Nanocomposites

From the previous results on neat hydrogels, HSFI-1:1.5 was selected as the matrix for the development of nanocomposite hydrogels.

G layers were introduced as conductive nanocarrier (0.2 wt.%). For that purpose, G was firstly homogenously dispersed in natural extracts containing water solution. As explained, Salvia extracts were used to facilitate the dispersion of G sheets in water (Shen et al., 2016). The picture of the obtained G containing nanocomposite hydrogel (HSFI-1:1.5GE) is shown in Figure 7.

Fig. 7. Photography of HSFI-1:1.5GE samples.

The effect of adding G nanosheets on the viscoelastic behavior of starch-based hydrogels was evaluated following the same methodology presented for the neat hydrogels. The corresponding results are shown in Figure 8.

It could be noticed that HSFI-1:1.5GE presented the same viscoelastic pattern as its counterpart without G (HSFI-1:1.5). Indeed, G' was higher than the loss modulus G'' and G' remained constant in the studied frequency range.

In addition, upon the addition of 0.2 wt.% of graphene, G' increased from 3660 ± 352 Pa for the unfilled hydrogel to 5680 ± 362 Pa for the nanocomposite. These results are in concordance with those reported by Ganguly et al. (2018) with G nanoreinforced acrylic hydrogels, where the G' was found to increase with increasing G content.

Fig. 8. Frequency sweep measurements results of G' (filled symbols) and G'' (empty symbols) of ▲ HSFI-1:1.5 and ◆ HSFI-1:1.5GE. Tests conditions: 37 °C and 10 Hz.

Antibacterial activity is also relevant issue when designing materials for being applied in biomedical applications. G is an outstanding candidate as antimicrobial agent (Gao et al., 2017; Grande et al., 2017), due to its capacity to inactivate and control various microorganisms proliferation (Zeng, Wang, Liu, & Zhang, 2017). Moreover, it is worth noting that Salvia extracts are also commonly used as effective antibacterial, antioxidant

and anti-inflammatory agent (Ghorbanpour, Hatami, Kariman, & Abbaszadeh Dahaji, 2016; Martins et al., 2014; Santamaria-Echart et al., 2018). The antimicrobial activity of G containing hydrogels was analyzed against *Escherichia coli* CECT 405 and *Staphylococcus aureus* CECT 239 bacteria. The inoculated samples were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h and 48 h and tested using the disc-plate antibiogram technique. The bacterial growth inhibition zones were measured (Figure 9).

The HSFI-1:1.5GE hydrogel presented inhibitory activity against both *E. coli* and *S. aureus* bacteria. After 24 h of incubation, an inhibitory halo of 7.0 mm was obtained in the case of *E. coli*, whereas for *S. aureus* the diameter reached up to 9.5 mm. Furthermore, it was observed that after 48 h of incubation, the size of the inhibition halo remains constant for *E. coli*. On the contrary, in the case of *S. aureus* the inhibition zone decreased from 9.5 mm to 4.5 mm. Nevertheless, the existence of the halo after 48 h denotes that the antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* bacteria keeps effective. Santamaria-Echart et al. (2018) reported that when high extracts contents are added into a waterborne polyurethane matrix, the resulting materials did not present antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*. However, in this work an effective antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* was obtained using significantly lower extracts content. Therefore, it seemed that, in our case, the antibacterial activity was also influenced by the addition of G sheets into the hydrogel matrix. Thus, it could be concluded that the incorporation of G dispersed in the *Salvia* extracts into the starch-based hydrogels led to efficient antibacterial materials.

Fig. 9. Antibacterial tests of HSF1-1:1.5GE for a) *E. coli* (duplicated) and *S. aureus* (duplicated) indicating the inhibition zones at 24 h (red line) and 48 h (black line).

The electrical response of HSF1-1:1.5 hydrogel with and without G was analyzed by electrical conductivity measurements by a two probe technique measuring the resulting current intensity for each applied voltage in the range of 0-5 V. G was incorporated as conductive nanofiller, thus it was expected the conductivity to be increased. From the measurements the electrical conductivity was calculated to be $1.23 \times 10^{-4} \text{ S m}^{-1}$ for the HSF1-1:1.5, whereas HSF1-1:1.5GE hydrogel showed an electrical conductivity of $1.16 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S m}^{-1}$. The increase of the conductivity up to a decade indicated that the G was acting as effective conductor nanoreinforcement of the hydrogel.

Ganguly et al. (2018) reported the value of 0.36 vol% of G as that for the percolation threshold in G containing acrylic hydrogels. However, the percolation threshold is strongly dependent on the nature and chemical structure of the macromolecular network and the created conductive pathway.

4. Conclusions

As hypothesized, starch-based hydrogels were successfully obtained by DA reaction between furan-modified starch and the BMI cross-linker in aqueous media. The effectiveness of DA reaction to form starch-based hydrogels was demonstrated by FTIR and UV-spectroscopy. As considered, the furan:maleimide weight ratio was found to affect significantly the rheological properties and the microstructure of the final hydrogels, decreasing the pore size and increasing the storage modulus value with the 1:1.5 ratio. Graphene nanosheets were incorporated as conductive nanofiller to the reaction medium using Salvia extracts as dispersion stabilizers. As expected, the obtained nanocomposite hydrogel presented not only mechanical improvement but also antimicrobial activity against both gram positive and gram negative bacteria and the conductivity of the material was improved in a decade. These biobased novel materials have promising properties in view of future biomedical applications, in particular those were electrical responsive hydrogels could be required.

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